

USING TECHNOLOGY TO ENHANCE ASSESSMENT OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The article considers the issue of effective methods of teaching a foreign language in primary school. For students to better master vocabulary, phonetics, grammar, etc., teachers turn to various methods of teaching a foreign language. In this case, the game method of teaching a language is effective, when students are involved in interactive classes, better learn English, sometimes without realizing that they are learning. Given the positive impact of game technology, they should be included in the process of teaching children. This will allow students to learn independently, and teachers will only be guides in the learning process. When they learn through play, students think about the information that they retain in their memory, this makes them creators of knowledge, and not just repeaters of information.*

Keywords. *Primary school, teaching methods, teaching a foreign language, foreign language.*

Introduction. The primary school teacher has a huge responsibility, he must instill in the young student the desire to discover the world, and increase motivation to study a foreign language, which opens the door to a new culture, a new lifestyle and new social relationships. It is important to teach children to perceive information in the lesson as useful and necessary for a successful future, perhaps a future profession. Undoubtedly, the purpose of the lesson is not only to study grammar and expand vocabulary. The student must realize the importance of studying foreign languages and cultural characteristics of other countries. Of course, the purpose of the lesson is not only to learn grammar and expand vocabulary. The student should realize the importance of learning foreign languages and cultural characteristics of other countries. Different methods are

used to teach a foreign language. Using the right teaching methods will help motivate both teachers and students. As teachers see their students improving, they become inspired by their teaching ideas. Once teachers become more motivated and enthusiastic about teaching their students, learning a foreign language becomes more enjoyable for students.

In elementary grades, foreign language teaching is often implemented in the form of reading adapted literature, doing written exercises in a notebook, listening, and working with pictures, cards, and illustrations. For a comprehensive assessment, monotonous tests and tests are usually used. It is worth noting that the use of such a method practically does not allow the student to develop oral speech: even with a conscious understanding and memorization of the basics of grammar and writing, difficulties may arise when trying to apply existing knowledge in a free conversation in a foreign language. To achieve effectiveness in the classroom, you can combine such a method, for example, with the communicative method. The main idea is not just memorizing grammar rules, but immersing the student in the language environment by studying literature in the original spelling, watching original cartoons, active work in pairs and mini-groups, and a large amount of speaking practice.

Listening is one of the important components of learning a foreign language. English grammar lessons will sparkle with new colours when audiobooks and podcasts are included in the lessons. The use of songs also helps students concentrate on the lessons - singing out loud, and listening to grammar examples is very fun and useful. Songs are easier to remember than regular texts. There are many fun, educational games for learning English - fillwords, crosswords, puzzles, rebuses, anagrams, etc. These activities help with grammar, and improve vocabulary and language skills. To motivate students, teachers use relevant, attractive content, and topics, and form an active vocabulary. Thus, a healthy, friendly atmosphere is undoubtedly maintained in the classroom, which contributes to the implementation of creative tasks, and interaction with each other and with

the teacher. Children responsibly complete the proposed tasks, and their language barrier and fears associated with communication in English disappear.

Conclusion. The methodology of teaching a foreign language to pupils in primary school should be based on some principles: learning through communication and interaction with people; the most individual approach to pupils; interesting, useful, relevant information as the basis of the lesson; increasing motivation for learning the language; integrating a foreign language with other subjects. Children of primary school age respond well to interactive lessons that stimulate imagination and creativity: they are ready to try something new and want to enjoy their learning in a familiar environment where they are comfortable speaking. This age group is ready and able to master new languages, and the benefits of learning a foreign language in primary school are many. Primary school students are more likely to learn how to work in a group and establish friendly relationships with their peers.

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